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**Eudaimonic and Uncertainty Metaphors about Life are Associated with Meaningfulness,
Experiential Avoidance, Mental Health and Happiness.**

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Abstract

Metaphors are frequently used in psychological interventions, as they are assumed to have effects on cognition and behavior. However, empirical research on this subject is still scarce. This research aims to identify possible types of metaphors that people use to understand life and to analyze the relationships between life metaphors, meaningfulness, experiential avoidance, happiness and mental health. A total of 1536 individuals from Spain and Latin America responded to a survey on the use of life metaphors, which also collected data on their feelings of meaning in life as well as levels of experiential avoidance, happiness, anxiety, depression and general mental health. In Part 1, using Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), two independent types of life metaphors were identified, i.e. eudaimonic metaphors (e.g. life is a treasure) and uncertainty metaphors (e.g. life is a maze). Moreover, other complex metaphors referred to fiction (e.g. life is a stage play, a dream) and confinement (e.g. life is a prison) were analyzed in relation to eudaimonic and uncertainty dimensions. In Part 2, eudaimonic metaphors were found associated with higher levels of happiness and meaningfulness, and lower levels of experiential avoidance, anxiety, depression and mental health problems. Conversely, uncertainty metaphors were associated with lower happiness and meaning in life, higher experiential avoidance, and higher presence of mental health symptoms. The results are coherent with the idea that, in clinical contexts, metaphors can be remarkable indicators of psychological problems and also offer an interesting tool for intervention.

Key words: metaphors; mental health; happiness; meaning in life; experiential avoidance

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Introduction

Currently in psychology, there is a growing interest in the analysis of how language tools play a decisive role in cognition. Language, through its connections with thoughts and the regulation of inner mental life, is also assumed to impact the subjective well-being experienced by individuals. Specifically, metaphors have been revealed as one of the linguistic tools that people use to make sense and orientate themselves when faced with complex, unfamiliar or difficult experiences (Baldwin et al., 2018). Research on metaphors has shown that they influence the way we conceptualize reality, reason about it, make decisions and take action (Thibodeau & Boroditsky, 2011, 2013, 2015). For these reasons, metaphors are frequently used in psychotherapy, as they contribute to mapping difficult areas of the client's life and may provide insights on adaptive patterns of behavior. For instance, Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) (Hayes et al., 2011), based on the Relational Frame Theory (RFT) account of language and thought (Hayes et al., 2001), uses metaphors extensively to promote mental health and well-being through increasing psychological flexibility, i.e. the capacity to engage in meaningful actions without avoiding the potentially disturbing inner experiences that may arise (Stoddard & Afari, 2014; Törneke, 2017, 2020).

Employing a metaphor implies assuming perspectives, beliefs, and assumptions on which it is based; indeed, a metaphor is an invitation to a way of life (Zemach, 1994) or a mindset towards life (Schmidt & Brdar, 2012). However, empirical research on how particular life metaphors are associated with meaningfulness, experiential avoidance, and beneficial outcomes is still scarce.

How metaphors work

Metaphors connect two semantic networks, making it possible to see one conceptual domain in terms of another. For instance, "life is a journey" invites the reader to use the semantic network of

travels to approach a different domain, i.e. life. In this regard, a conceptual metaphor establishes a bridge between a domain of reality a person is familiar with and another domain that is more diffuse, and usually, also more abstract and challenging. Metaphors allow us to approach the latter in terms of the former, offering a cognitive map for dealing with complex events or highly abstract concepts (Boroditsky, 2000; Gentner & Bowdle, 2008; Kövecses, 2010; Lakoff & Johnson, 1980). A metaphor entails a "source" domain, i.e. the conceptual domain from which the metaphor is drawn, and a "target" domain, i.e. the conceptual field that is to be understood by means of the metaphor (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980). The second term of the metaphorical "A is B" structure, the source domain, is usually a highly representative prototype or exemplar of the category to which both terms belong (Ortony, 1986, p. 349). For example, in the metaphor "life is a journey", "journey" is the more familiar, known and concrete source conceptual domain, by which the more complex and abstract target domain, "life", is attempted to be comprehended. Connections can be easily established between both domains: both life and travel involve movement in time and space; the metaphor allows the individuals to understand themselves as travelers, their life goals as destinations, the means to accomplish goals as paths, life difficulties as obstacles in the journey, etc.

Cognitive psycholinguistics has provided an interesting account of how metaphors work, based on the concept of simulation. For instance, Gibbs (2006) and Gibbs and Matlock (2008) have argued that understanding many kinds of metaphorical expressions requires building a simulation whereby the readers imagine what it must be like to perform bodily actions and engage in activities referred to in the metaphor. An example is taking journeys as the source domain for constructing a metaphor, as in "life is a journey". According to these authors, understanding this metaphor requires that readers engage in an experiential or embodied simulation (i.e. a mental recreation of bodily processes) of travel-related situations (e.g. bodily actions and sensations associated with movement) that may activate a schema (e.g. moving from a source along a path to arrive a destination or, schematically, SOURCE-PATH-GOAL). Then, this schema is mapped onto a different domain (e.g.

life) to provide some understanding of it (e.g. life involves movement through a series of vicissitudes from birth to death). Keith Oatley's account of fictional works has also provided remarkable insights on metaphors. For this author, fiction is a simulation of human actions that readers run in their minds just as computer simulations run in computers, and metaphors are at the core of fictional works (Oatley, 1999, 2001, 2011). In fact, metaphor is the term for simulation in literary language (Oatley, 2001), a simulation that allows us to discover new meanings and produce deeper mental models of ourselves, others, and social interactions (Oatley, 2001, 2011). Some examples are seeing life itself as a dream, as Shakespeare repeatedly proposes, and seeing fictional works as dreams, as Oatley (2011) suggests. When the readers run such simulations in their minds some cognitive and emotional effects are produced thereby (Oatley, 1999). Through the use of metaphor our view of an aspect of reality may be transformed. For instance, the dream-based metaphor in Shakespearean theater may make us aware of distinctions between appearance and substance in life; and seeing fiction as dreams may suggest that plays, novels, poetry, films, stories, etc. are apart from ordinary life, constructed, but meaningful.

In the field of contextual behavioral science, metaphors have received great attention from Relational Frame Theory (RFT), a functionalist-contextualist approach to language and cognition (Hayes, 1994; Hayes et al., 2001). According to RFT, a metaphor entails two separate networks of relations that are connected through a physical or formal property, dimension, or relation. This coordination frame modifies the target's relations and transforms the target's functions (Stewart & Barnes-Holmes, 2001; Stewart et al., 2001). In short, metaphors work by effectively transferring features that are very evident in one event to a different event (Törneke, 2010). Interestingly, relating a conceptual network with another will have remarkable effects. Some functions of the target domain may be transformed as a result of understanding it in terms of the source domain (Stewart & Barnes-Holmes, 2001; Stewart et al., 2001).

Metaphors in Acceptance and Commitment Therapy

The interest in metaphors among psychologists has come hand in hand with their potential to contribute to therapeutic change. In particular, Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT), based on RFT, has succeeded in connecting basic research on metaphors with their applications in clinical and health psychology (Foody et al., 2014; McCurry & Hayes, 1992). The ACT approach aims at modifying the psychological functions of private events (thoughts, emotions, etc.) by altering the social/verbal context in which they occur, rather than attempting to change the form or frequency of such events (Hayes & Wilson, 1994). To this end, ACT makes extensive use of metaphors, paradoxes, experiential exercises, and other nonliteral forms of language (Wilson et al., 2001).

The ACT approach has shown effectiveness in the treatment of a variety of psychological problems, including anxiety disorders, depression, addiction, somatic health problems, chronic pain, and transdiagnostic conditions (A-tjak et al., 2015; Gloster et al., 2020). The mechanism of therapeutic change, as proposed in the ACT Hexaflex model (Wilson, 2007), is the increase of the individual's psychological flexibility throughout the therapeutic process. Psychological flexibility represents a style of approaching inner experiences on the basis of acceptance, as opposed to rigid control and rejection of potentially disturbing thoughts, emotions, memories, and sensations while engaging in actions aligned with personal values, although such behaviors may enact aversive inner experiences, as opposed to experiential avoidance.

Working with metaphors aims to promote psychological flexibility along the therapeutic process (Stoddart & Afari, 2014; Törneke, 2017; Törneke, 2020). Understanding problematic situations through metaphors may allow patients to identify the mechanisms of problem maintenance and guide them in finding solutions. Metaphors are also used to identify personal values and motivate engagement with meaningful behaviors (Stoddart & Afari, 2014). Moreover, the ease with which metaphor-based conceptualizations can be remembered prompts generalization of responses to situations in the patient's life (McCurry & Hayes, 1992; Otto, 2000).

Metaphors and Meaning in Life

Metaphors are mechanisms for constructing meaning (Kövecses, 2015). Psychotherapists consciously design and use metaphors to facilitate clients' discovery of new meanings and valued actions in their lives (Dahl et al., 2009; Foody et al., 2014; Stoddart & Afari, 2014). However, beyond therapeutic contexts, natural language is full of metaphors on life, revealing aspects of the meanings that people confer to their existence. Authors such as Benczes & Ságvári (2018a, 2018b), Köves (2002), Kövecses (2005, 2010) and Kuczok (2016) have analyzed the metaphors on life that people use in different languages, such as English, Hungarian and Polish. Their research has made it possible to draw up lists of life metaphors frequently used, identifying areas of commonality and also differences across languages. For example, viewing life as a journey, a story, a theatrical performance, a fight or war, or a game of chance, among others, are typical terms to talk about existence. Attempts to identify life metaphors in the Spanish-speaking context have been also carried out (Hoffman et al., 2021; Hoffman et al. 2015; Hoffman & Acosta-Orozco, 2015). The results found in Colombian samples indicated that metaphors with an active and moderately positive content, such as "life is a journey" and "life is an adventure", were highly preferred by participants. In contrast, metaphors with a negative affective component, such as "life is a prison" or "life is a war," were less preferred. Cross-cultural differences in preferences about life metaphors may be affected by the cultural and historical experiences of speech communities (Kövecses, 2005; Kuczok, 2016). However, the variation in the use of metaphors for life by particular speakers may be the result of a complex interplay between contextual variables (Kövecses, 2015, 2017), including social factors (Benczes & Ságvári, 2018a, 2018b).

Interestingly, metaphors about life used in everyday language may be addressing some components of the experience of meaning in life that psychological research has identified, i.e., comprehension/coherence, purpose, and mattering/significance (George & Park, 2016; Martela & Steger, 2016). For a person to experience meaning in life, he or she must be able to make sense of the

world and perceive it as comprehensible, coherent, and understandable. As mentioned, metaphors seek to structure the domains of experience, providing a network of meanings that give coherence and make events interpretable (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980). For example, viewing life as a journey uses travel-related schema to impose some order on the apparent chaos of life, structuring life as a movement from an origin to a destination and using travel-related elements (e.g., the stages of a journey, fellow travelers, making decisions about which paths to take, etc.) to understand life. In addition, feeling the meaning of life requires clarifying or identifying valuable life purposes. Again, some life metaphors can address the purpose-related aspect of the meaning of life. For example, "life is a journey" carries the idea of journey stages and a point of arrival that may correspond to life goals, vocation, life mission, etc. On the other hand, "life is a game of chance" and "life is a maze" may point to the lack of a clear destination-purpose or to difficulties in finding paths that lead to fulfilling one's life goals. Finally, experiencing meaning in life implies recognizing that life is important, worthwhile and significant. As mentioned, metaphors can be used to identify and mark valued aspects of life and meaningful courses of action (Dahl et al., 2009; Stewart et al., 2001; Stoddart & Afari, 2014). In this sense, metaphors such as "life is a gift" and "life is a treasure" guide the person to understand that life is a valuable and precious reality.

As mentioned, in metaphors the functions of the target-domain (e.g. life) are transformed, as this concept is now seen in the light of the source-domain (e.g. journey, gift, game of chance, maze, war, prison, etc.) (Stewart & Barnes-Holmes, 2001; Stewart et al., 2001). Here, life metaphors have psychological effects, as research has found. The participants in studies conducted by Hoffman and Acosta-Orozco (2015) and Hoffman et al. (2015) reported that their life metaphor had a high impact on their motivation and decision making processes. Baldwin et al. (2018) found that participants who conceptualized life using the journey metaphor experienced more meaning in life. Furthermore, the journey metaphor was found to be particularly beneficial for individuals who perceived low levels of coherence in life. By imagining life as a journey, people perceived greater interrelatedness between

life events, which in turn predicted a greater presence of meaning. In previous research, Landau et al. (2014) found that simple experimental metaphor-based interventions produced behavioral changes. For example, using the journey metaphor as a framework for conceptualizing personal academic identity increased engagement with study in a sample of undergraduates, whereas using a different metaphor -or not using a metaphor at all- did not yield this outcome.

Meaning in Life, Well-being and Experiential Avoidance

As presented, metaphor use has psychological effects. For this reason metaphors are viewed in psychotherapy as a tool to enhance adaptive psychological flexibility-related processes such as meaningfulness and experiential acceptance, aiming to promote well-being and mental health. Little is known on how life metaphors are connected with these psychological processes and beneficial outcomes. However, research has largely analyzed how meaning in life, experiential avoidance and well-being are connected to each other.

Psychological well-being is a complex construct referring to optimal psychological experience and functioning (Ryan & Deci, 2001). Previous research has considered psychological well-being in relation to both hedonic and eudaimonic elements (Dodge et al., 2012; Huta & Waterman, 2014). Huta and Waterman (2014) reviewed a variety of conceptualizations proposed for eudaimonic well-being and they found that definitions mainly referred to growth, meaning, authenticity, excellence, positive relations, engagement/flow and acceptance as core elements of eudaimonia. For instance, a widespread eudaimonic conceptualization of psychological well-being assumes that it is a multidimensional construct (Ryff, 1989, 2014; Ryff & Singer, 2008), which combines presence of meaning, direction and purpose in life (purpose in life), living according to personal convictions (autonomy), use of personal capabilities and development potential (personal growth), management of life situations (control of the environment), depth of relationships with significant others (positive relationships), and knowledge and acceptance of oneself and one's personal limitations (self-acceptance). Hedonic well-being, on the other hand, mainly refers to

elements such as pleasure, enjoyment, happiness, life satisfaction, positive affect, low negative affect, and low distress (Dodge et al., 2012; Huta & Waterman, 2014).

Empirical research has consistently found that the presence of meaning in life is associated with psychological well-being, either concerning eudaimonic and hedonic aspects (Compton, 2000; Cotton Bronk et al., 2009; Crego et al., 2020; Scannell et al., 2002; Schnell, 2009; Steger et al., 2006; Steger et al., 2009; Steger & Kashdan, 2007). Moreover, experiencing meaning in life is connected with mental health, whereas perceived meaninglessness is linked to anxiety and depression-related symptoms (Glaw et al., 2017).

Interestingly, the presence of meaning in life is negatively associated with experiential avoidance (Kashdan & Kane, 2011; Kelso et al., 2020; Machell et al., 2015; Yela et al., 2020). Experiential avoidance is defined as the individual's tendency to avoid potentially disturbing inner experiences (i.e., thoughts, emotions, memories, and sensations), although doing so may lead to unwanted consequences in the long-term and may divert the person from achieving his/her goals and values, i.e., what is meaningful for the person (Hayes et al., 2011). Current psychology has proposed experiential avoidance as a transdiagnostic process operating at the basis of a variety of psychological problems (Akbari et al., 2022; Barlow et al., 2017; Boulanger et al., 2010), as it has been found to be negatively associated with mental health (Chawla & Ostafin, 2007; Yela et al., 2020) and well-being (Machell et al., 2015). Taking these relationships into account, experiential avoidance is presently considered a key process to be targeted in psychological interventions, especially ACT-based interventions (Hayes & Wilson, 1994; Hayes et al., 2011).

The Present Research

Our research builds on three pillars: 1) insights from cognitive linguistics on the use of metaphors in natural language, 2) contributions from RFT and ACT on how language tools may be used to increase meaning and psychological flexibility, as opposed to experiential avoidance, and 3)

literature on the relationships between feeling meaning in life, experiential avoidance, mental health, and psychological well-being.

In this context, we conducted a two-part investigation. Part 1 was aimed at knowing which life metaphors are preferentially endorsed among Spanish-speaking people. In addition, we analyzed how different life metaphors may be connected with each other, and tried to identify groups of metaphors on life.

Part 2 was carried out to explore the connections between the life metaphors a person endorses and his/her levels of meaningfulness, well-being, mental health, and psychological flexibility. As mentioned, metaphors are tools intended to provide meaning to experiential domains, giving structure, coherence and purpose. Following this idea, we explored whether life metaphors are associated with the presence of meaning in life. Previous research has found that feeling meaning in life is associated with subjective well-being, mental health, and perceived physical health (Czekierda et al., 2017; Li et al., 2021; Glaw et al., 2017; Scannell et al., 2002; Schnell, 2009; Steger, 2017; Steger, 2018). In the Spanish-speaking context, Crego et al. (2020) found strong correlations between the feeling of meaning in life and positive well-being (life satisfaction, happiness, positive affect), and negative associations with negative affect and mental health problems. In this line, we analyzed a possible connection between the use of life metaphors, well-being and mental health. Experiential avoidance is negatively associated with the presence of meaning in life (Kashdan & Kane, 2011; Kelso et al., 2020; Machell et al., 2015; Yela et al., 2020) and has been proposed as a key process involved in mental health and well-being (Akbari et al., 2022; Barlow et al., 2017; Eustis et al., 2020; Hayes & Wilson, 1994; Hayes et al., 2011). Therefore, exploring the potential relationship between life metaphors and experiential avoidance is also an interesting issue.

Method

Participants

The participants were 1536 individuals (83% female) from Spain and Latin America. The mean age was 40.65 years ($Sd = 16.86$), with participants ranging from 18 to 82 years old. Most of the participants came from Venezuela (28.7%), Argentina (23.2%), Mexico (12%), Colombia (10.4%), Nicaragua (6.2%), and Spain (5%), with other nationalities contributing with percentages below 5%. Almost half of the sample (45.7%) reported having a university degree, 13.4% had postgraduate studies, 18.2% studied up to high school level, 18% received professional education, and 4.7% elementary education. Participants in active work represented 36.1% of the total sample, with 21.4% students, 20.6% unemployed persons, 13.3% retirees, and 8.6% reporting other labor situations.

Procedure

Data collection was carried out by an online survey that included, in addition to sociodemographic data, a questionnaire on life metaphors, measures of meaningfulness and experiential avoidance, and measures of mental health and well-being. The questionnaire was designed using Google Forms. Participants were recruited through social media postings, where a link to access the survey was included. The online questionnaire included an outline of the research, which was presented as an investigation aimed at learning more about how participants understand their lives and gathering information on their levels of subjective well-being. They were also informed that all answers would be anonymously collected. The participants filled in the questionnaire voluntarily and without receiving any compensation. Data collection took place from July to September 2021. This research obtained the approval of the Ethics Committee of the [Blinded Name of Institution] (Minutes of the meeting 28/05/2021). Informed consent was received from all participants.

Part 1

Objectives

This first part was exploratory in nature. We tried to find out which metaphors about life are most commonly used in a sample of Spanish speakers. In addition, we tried to identify possible groups of life metaphors.

Methods

Instruments

A questionnaire on the use of life metaphors was included. As some authors have pointed out, a single source domain is not sufficient to encompass all aspects of the target domain (Benczes & SÁgvári, 2018; Kövecses, 2010), with individuals frequently employing several metaphors, to varying degrees, to understand the target semantic domain. A total of 19 metaphors about life were selected, taking into account those that have been identified as most common by previous research (Benczes & SÁgvári, 2018a, 2018b; Köves, 2002; Kövecses, 2005, 2010; Kuczok, 2016; Lakoff & Johnson, 1980) especially in the Spanish-speaking domain (Hoffman et al., 2021; Hoffman et al. 2015; Hoffman & Acosta-Orozco, 2015). Specifically, the questionnaire included the following metaphors: "life is a... journey/ book or a movie/ gift/ box full of experiences/ lottery or game of chance/ treasure/ course of a river/ war or battle/ maze/ riddle or puzzle/ school or teacher/ dream/ sports competition/ stage play/ house or building/ carnival/ adventure/ roller coaster/ jail or prison". Participants were asked to indicate the extent to which they agreed with each of the ways of understanding/referring to life. Each metaphor was rated on a Likert-type scale from 1 ("Strongly disagree") to 7 ("Strongly agree").

Data Analyses

Basic descriptive analyses (means, standard deviations) were carried out in order to identify which metaphors received greater endorsement as ways of understanding life. We also analyzed possible differences by sex, using *t*-test for independent samples. The association between the use of metaphors and age was assessed using Pearson's *r* correlation.

The total sample of participants was randomly divided into two halves ($n_1 = 758$; $n_2 = 778$) in order to implement procedures based on factor analysis. This analysis strategy is intended to identify underlying metaphors groupings in the questionnaire used. First, an Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was carried out, using one of the two halves of the sample. Principal component analysis was used as the extraction method, and factors with Eigenvalues greater than 1 were retained. Direct Oblimin (with delta = 0) rotation method was used to improve interpretability of factors. Next, the identified factorial structure was further evaluated by conducting Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) on the other half of the sample.

Exploratory analyses were carried out using the SPSS 19 statistical package software (IBM, Armonk, USA) and confirmatory analyses were carried out using AMOS 16 structural equation analysis software (IBM, Armonk, USA).

Results

Descriptive analyses

Means and standard deviations for metaphors endorsement are presented in Table 1. Independent samples *t*-tests revealed gender differences for the metaphors life is a lottery or game of chance ($t_{353.52} = -1.99$, $p = .048$), maze ($t_{1534} = -1.99$, $p = .048$), sport competition ($t_{1534} = 2.23$, $p = .026$), and roller-coaster ($t_{1534} = -2.12$, $p = .034$).

Exploratory identification metaphors latent groupings

The KMO statistic ($KMO = .88$) and a significant Bartlett's test of sphericity ($\chi^2 = 5807.95$, $df = 171$, $p = .000$) revealed the adequacy of the sample for EFA. The analysis produced three factors (Table 2), which jointly explained 53.27% of the variance. However, the three-factor solution presented some problems. First, Factor 3 added only 5.37% of explained variance and consisted only of negatively loading items. The items with the highest loadings on this factor (life is... a book or a movie/dream/sports competition/stage play/carnival) also presented strong cross-loads on the other two factors. In addition, some items clearly loading on Factor 1 and Factor 2 also presented weaker

loadings on Factor 3. In fact, intercorrelations equal to $-.40$ and $-.32$ between Factor 3 and Factor 1 and Factor 2, respectively, were found, while Factor 1 and Factor 2 interfactor correlation was just of $-.09$. Second, the metaphor "life is a jail or prison" was also problematic, as it presented similar loadings in Factors 1 and 2. Finally, the determinant of the correlation matrix equal to $.000$ ($<.00001$) indicated the presence of potential multicollinearity problems.

In order to overcome these difficulties and achieve a clearer interpretation of the latent groups of metaphors, a second EFA was carried out ($KMO = .85$; Bartlett's test of sphericity: $\chi^2 = 3757.81$, $df = 78$, $p = .000$; Correlation matrix determinant = $.007$) eliminating those items that were problematic. The resulting structure yielded two clearly differentiated factors (Table 2) which were able to jointly account for 53.27% of the total variance. The interfactor correlation was $.02$.

Confirmatory factor analyses of latent groups of life metaphors

First, we carried out a CFA aimed to replicate the three-factor structure obtained in the first EFA. The metaphor "life is a jail or prison" was not considered, as it presented similar cross-loads on two factors. As expected, the three-factor CFA model did not present adequate fit indices ($\chi^2 = 1055.71$, $df = 132$, $p = .000$; $\chi^2/df = 8.00$, $AGFI = .81$, $NFI = .83$, $CFI = .85$, $SRMR = .10$, $RMSEA = .10$).

Based on the above results of the second EFA, a second CFA was carried out in order to assess a two-factor structure. The life metaphors journey/ gift/ box full of experiences/ treasure/ course of a river/ school or teacher/ house or building/ adventure were taken as observable variables related to a first underlying latent variable (Factor 1). The metaphors presenting life as a lottery or game of chance/ war or battle/ maze/ riddle or puzzle/ roller coaster were linked to a second latent variable (Factor 2). The correlation between the errors associated with the metaphors "gift" and "treasure", which appeared to be strongly associated ($r = .84$, $p = .000$), was allowed for in the analyses. This first CFA produced, however, results indicating a rather marginal fit of data to the two-factor structure ($\chi^2 = 331.20$, $df = 63$, $p = .000$; $\chi^2/df = 5.26$, $AGFI = .91$, $NFI = .93$, $CFI = .94$,

$SRMR = .08$, $RMSEA = .07$). Covariance between factors was not significant ($Cov. Estimate = -.06$, $S.E. = 0.08$, $p = .482$). Considering that both the EFA and the CFA had indicated the absence of association between the two latent factors, we proceeded to analyze the two metaphors' clusters independently. The corresponding confirmatory analyses showed a very good fit, both for the one-factor structure consisting of the metaphors journey/ gift/ box full of experiences/ treasure/ river course/ school or teacher/ house or building/ adventure ($\chi^2 = 52.88$, $df = 19$, $p = .000$; $\chi^2/df = 2.78$, $AGFI = .97$, $NFI = .98$, $CFI = .99$, $SRMR = .02$, $RMSEA = .05$), and for the one-factor structure consisting of the metaphors lottery or game of chance/ war or battle/ maze/ riddle or puzzle/ roller coaster ($\chi^2 = 8.86$, $df = 5$, $p = .115$; $\chi^2/df = 1.77$, $AGFI = .99$, $NFI = .99$, $CFI = .99$, $SRMR = .02$, $RMSEA = .03$).

An additional CFA was conducted in order to find out whether those metaphors loading in a third factor in the first EFA (book or movie/dream/sports competition/stage play/carnival) could constitute a separate group. However, the single-factor structure tested yielded poor fit indices ($\chi^2 = 32.18$, $df = 5$, $p = .000$; $\chi^2/df = 6.44$, $AGFI = .95$, $NFI = .96$, $CFI = .96$, $SRMR = .03$, $RMSEA = .08$).

Further exploration of metaphors in a two-dimensional space

As suggested by both EFA and CFA analyses, the clearest way to understand life metaphors may be using two independent factors. In this regard, we conducted an additional factor analysis, using the total sample ($N = 1536$) to test the usefulness of using a two-dimensional space to locate life metaphors, especially those with strong cross-loads (i.e. movie/ dream/ sports, competition/stage play/carnival/jail or prison). In this additional EFA, a two-factor solution with Varimax rotation was forced, in order to position all items within an orthogonal space ($KMO = .90$; Bartlett's test of sphericity: $\chi^2 = 12124.29$, $df = 171$, $p = .000$). The results are presented in Figure 1. The axes basically corresponded to the two previously found, Factor 1 and Factor 2, which, as will be argued in the Discussion Part 1, may be labeled as eudaimonia (horizontal axis) and uncertainty (vertical axis) dimensions. As presented in Figure 1, metaphorical terms such as book or movie, dream, sports

competition, stage play, and carnival appeared positioned in the quadrant indicative of eudaimonia and uncertainty. The prison metaphor appeared located in the low eudaimonia and high uncertainty quadrant.

Metaphors where life is viewed as a journey/ gift/ box full of experiences/ treasure/ course of a river/ school or teacher/ house or building/ adventure (i.e. Factor 1), overall, were located in intermediate positions in relation to the vertical axis (Factor 2). The metaphors presenting life as a lottery or game of chance/ war or battle/ maze/ riddle or puzzle/ roller coaster (i.e. Factor 2) were positioned around intermediate positions in relation to the horizontal axis (Factor 1). This result reinforces the idea that Factor 1 and Factor 2 may be understood as independent dimensions. Moreover, this further exploration suggests that the use of two dimensions may be helpful in characterizing metaphors with hybrid features.

Discussion Part 1

Part 1 revealed that most of the life metaphors included in the questionnaire received moderate to high endorsement by participants, considering the items range of response. This result is coherent with previous research carried out in the Spanish-speaking context, where metaphors such as life is a journey, gift, adventure, roller-coaster, or school were highly preferred by respondents (Hoffman & Acosta-Orozco, 2015; Hoffman et al., 2015; Hoffman et al., 2021). Other metaphors, such as life is a jail or prison, received low endorsement in our study, which is also similar to previous studies conducted in Latin America. In addition, our results are coherent with research conducted among participants using different languages despite the different methodological approaches used. For instance, assimilating life to a precious possession, a gift, a journey, a container, a maze, a puzzle, a gamble, or a war is present among American-English, Hungarian and Polish speakers (Kuczok, 2016). This finding may be pointing to some potentially near-universal aspects on which some life metaphors (e.g., life is a journey) could be based, such as the idea that long-term purposeful activities are journeys (Kövecses, 2005) or the image schema SOURCE-

PATH-GOAL emerging from the elementary universal experience of walking along a path (Kövecses, 2015). However, despite commonalities in the use of life metaphors, each speech community may also present cultural differences concerning the content and predominance of some metaphors (Kövecses, 2005). In this regard, Kövecses (2005) introduces the concept of “preferential conceptualization”, that occurs when languages/cultures share many of the same conceptual metaphors for a target domain (e.g. life) but a different set of such available metaphors is preferred by speakers of the different languages. For instance, in our study among Spanish-speakers, the metaphor “life is a journey” was highly endorsed, which is similar to the preferences of Poles but differs from Hungarians as the latter preferentially viewed life as a “war/struggle”, a metaphor less commonly used by Spanish-speakers (Kuczok, 2016).

Particularly interesting is the identification of two types of life metaphors. Results revealed a first group of metaphors, including views of life as a journey/ gift/ box full of experiences/ treasure/ course of a river/ school or teacher/ house or building/ adventure, which can be characterized by their eudaimonic character. Eudaimonia is a term that harks back to Aristotle’s *Nicomachean Ethics* and his idea of the good life. In current psychology, as mentioned, this construct includes elements such as the presence of meaning in life, purpose, growth, authenticity, excellence, flow, competence, acceptance/self-acceptance, etc. (Huta & Waterman, 2014). To a greater or lesser extent, these aspects would be implicit in this first group of metaphors. For example, the journey and the course of a river imply a destination or purpose while a gift or a treasure represents something intrinsically valuable. A school, a teacher, or building a house entails the idea of growth and adventures and life experiences are occasions to grow, be autonomous, demonstrate competence, feel engaged with a course of action, and so on. Furthermore, as will be discussed in Part 2 of this study, this first group of metaphors is expected to be strongly associated with eudaimonia-related variables, such as the presence of meaning in life and the acceptance of experiences.

In addition, a second group of life metaphors, such as lottery or game of chance/ war or battle/ maze/ enigma or puzzle/ roller coaster, appeared to emphasize the uncertain side of existence. The analyses carried out showed that the use of eudaimonic metaphors and metaphors of uncertainty was relatively independent, as no correlation between both types of metaphors was found. Therefore, we could find individuals who obtain high scores in both types of metaphors (high eudaimonia and high uncertainty), low scores in both (low eudaimonia and low uncertainty), or agreement with one metaphorical understanding life but not with the other (high eudaimonia and low uncertainty; low eudaimonia and high uncertainty).

A group of metaphors assimilating life to a fiction (book or movie/dream/sports competition/play/ carnival) cross-loaded on other factors and produced a third negatively defined marginal factor obscuring the interpretation of the first EFA analysis. Nevertheless, these metaphors deserved further exploration. Interestingly, Oatley (2001) has analyzed how metaphors may act as simulations by modeling some aspects of reality, taking Shakespeare's use of such metaphors as a starting point. For example, in *A Midsummer Night's Dream* life is mirrored to a dream and in *The Tempest* (Act 4, Scene 1) it is said that "We are such stuff/ As dreams are made on, and our little life/ Is rounded with a sleep". Also in *Hamlet's* famous monologue (Act 3, Scene 1), death is equated with sleep. In *Macbeth* (Act 5, Scene 5), metaphors such as life is "a walking shadow", "a poor player", "a tale told by an idiot" appear. In *The Merchant of Venice* (Act 1, Scene 1) and *As You Like It* (Act 2 Scene 7), the world is likened to a stage in which individuals are mere players. Following Oatley (2001), by using these metaphors Shakespeare may be suggesting the contrast between the surface (the shadow, the dream, the appearance of a performance) and the substance of life's events. Moreover, through such metaphors, Shakespeare would also be providing us with a revolutionary understanding of fiction: the idea that theater, poetry and stories are a reflection, a simulation of life.

Viewing life as a dream is also a prototypical life metaphor in Spanish literature. The playwright Pedro Calderón de la Barca puts a question in the mouth of the captive Segismundo:

“What is life?” His answer emphasizes the unreality and ambivalence of life by using metaphors: “A madness / What is life? A thing that seems /A mirage that falsely gleams /Phantom joy, delusive rest / Since is life a dream at best /And even dreams themselves are dreams” (Translation by Denis Florence Mac-Carthy in *Calderon's Dramas*, pp. 78-79. London: Henry S. King & Co, 1873).

Taken together, these metaphors apparently indicate the degree to which the person perceives life as something unreal (dream), a work of fiction (book or movie) or a performance (sports show, stage play, wearing a costume or mask at Carnival). However, along with such unreality, fiction or representation nuance, these metaphors may entail both eudaimonic and uncertainty connotations.

From a psychometric point of view, the most parsimonious and data-driven solution was to consider such fictional metaphors, as well as the prison metaphor, using two dimensions (i.e. eudaimonia and uncertainty) that had emerged from factor analyses. In this regard, the fictional metaphors may be referring to both eudaimonic and uncertainty aspects. For example, following Oatley's approach, the dream metaphor may include a component of meaningfulness (i.e. eudaimonia) and at the same time may be pointing to life as something unreal, where appearance and substance can be differentiated (i.e. a component of uncertainty) (Oatley, 2011). This duality would be present in the other metaphors of this group (book or movie, stage play, sports competition, carnival). For example, a dream can be interpreted as an illusion, a carnival is a party, a book/film/stage play is an ordered succession of chapters or scenes with a plot developing towards an end, and playing a sport implies following rules and pursuing the game objectives, which are eudaimonic components. But at the same time, a competition implies rivalry and struggle, a carnival implies uncertainty as to who is behind the mask, and playing a role on stage can be interpreted as "falsehood".

The metaphor "life is a jail or prison" deserves a separate comment. This metaphor, which was the least endorsed item, produced cross-loads on the eudaimonic factor (negatively) and on the uncertainty factor (positively), as the first EFA revealed. From a methodological point of view, an

item loading on both factors is problematic. Nevertheless, as a metaphor considered individually, it is an interesting item, since it reveals a perception of life as both uncertain and meaningless, as a further analysis confirmed. The metaphors of confinement also have a long tradition in literature, as Fludernik (2019) analyzed. Frequently, prison has been metaphorically used as a counterworld, with the imprisonment reflecting ideas of suffering, condemnation, misery, punishment, oppression, darkness/ignorance, lack of control, etc., which represent an inverted image of valuable and eudaimonic aspects of life (happiness, light/knowledge, humanity, socializing, active self-determination) (Fludernik, 2019). From an applied point of view (e.g., at clinical psychology work) the use of this metaphor by an individual could presumably be indicative of low levels of well-being and may be a cause of concern. This aspect will be further explored in Part 2.

Regardless, characterizing these complex, hybrid, life metaphors using just two dimensions does not exhaust all the possibilities of analysis. For this reason, we also recommend the use of other methodologies, and particularly, qualitative research, that will better capture other nuances of fictional metaphors and confinement metaphors.

Part 2

Objectives and hypotheses

The second part of our study is aimed to analyze the relationship between using eudaimonic metaphors and uncertainty metaphors and feelings of meaning in life, experiential avoidance, mental health and happiness. Specifically, we propose two hypotheses:

H1: The use of eudaimonic metaphors will be associated with higher levels of meaningfulness, lower levels of experiential avoidance (i.e. higher psychological flexibility), and greater happiness and negatively associated with anxiety, depression, and mental illness symptoms.

H2: The use of uncertainty metaphors will be associated with lower levels of meaningfulness, higher experiential avoidance (i.e. lower psychological flexibility), and lower happiness scores as

well as being positively associated with anxiety, depression, and general symptoms of mental health problems.

Methods

Instruments

Life metaphors. Based on the results of Part 1, we calculated two scores for metaphor use. The score for eudaimonic metaphors endorsement was calculated by averaging the 8 items corresponding to the metaphors journey/ gift/ box full of experiences/ treasure/ river course/ school or teacher/ house or building/ adventure. Cronbach's alpha reliability was $\alpha=.86$ for the total sample. The score for the use of uncertainty metaphors was calculated by averaging the 5 corresponding items (lottery or game of chance/ war or battle/ maze/ riddle or puzzle/ roller coaster). Cronbach's alpha reliability was $\alpha=.81$ for the total sample.

Meaning in Life. The feelings of meaning in life were measured using the 5-item Presence of Meaning subscale of the Meaning in Life Questionnaire (MLQ) (Steger et al., 2006; Spanish translation of the items, developed by Steger and Zaccagnini, that is available at the original author's website: <http://www.michaelfsteger.com/wp-content/uploads/2013/03/MLQ-Spanish.doc>). This measure assesses to what extent the respondents feel their lives have meaning. An item example is 'My life has a clear sense of purpose'. Participants responded to each item on a 7-point Likert-type scale, where 1=Absolutely Untrue and 7=Absolutely True. Total scores are calculated averaging the 5 items of the subscale, with higher scores (range 1-7) representing higher levels of meaning in life experienced. Internal consistency reliability for the Presence of Meaning items was $\alpha=.88$.

Experiential avoidance. The 7-item Acceptance and Action Questionnaire (AAQ-II) was used (Bond et al., 2011; Spanish adaptation by Patrón Espinosa, 2010). This scale assesses the respondent's unwillingness to be exposed to and accept potentially disturbing inner experiences (e.g., thoughts, feelings, memories, sensations) even when avoidant behavior could be inconsistent with

the individual's values and goals. An example item is 'My painful experiences and memories make it difficult for me to live a life that I would value'. In this sample, reliability was $\alpha = .92$.

Happiness. The 4-item Subjective Happiness Scale (SHS) was used (Lyubomirsky & Lepper, 1999; Spanish version by Extremera & Fernández-Berrocal, 2014). This measure assesses the respondents' global level of perceived happiness. Two items ask respondents to report the extent to which they consider themselves to be a happy or unhappy person, in absolute terms (e.g. 'In general, I consider myself: 1 = Not a very happy person/ 7 = A very happy person') and relative to other people (e.g., 'Compared to most of my peers, I consider myself: 1= Less happy/ 7 = More happy'). The other two items present descriptions of happy and unhappy people, and respondents are requested to indicate the extent to which each description applies to themselves (e.g., 'Some people are generally not very happy. Although they are not depressed, they never seem as happy as they might be. To what extent does this characterization describe you?: 1 = Not at all/ 7 = A great deal'). All items are rated on a 7-point Likert-type scale. Total scores were calculated for each participant, averaging responses to the four items (range 1-7), with higher scores indicating greater perceived happiness. The internal consistency reliability was $\alpha=0.87$.

Mental health issues. The Spanish version of the GHQ-12 was used (Rocha, et al. 2011). Goldberg's 12-item General Health Questionnaire (GHQ-12; Goldberg & Williams, 1988) is a screening instrument designed to identify individuals with possible diagnosable psychological disorders. An example item is 'Over the past few weeks, have you felt constantly under strain?' Participants are asked to respond to each question on a 4-point Likert-type scale, from 0 to 3, with higher scores indicating that the symptoms/problems have been recently present more than usual. A total score (range 0-3) was calculated for each participant, averaging the individual's responses to the twelve items. Cronbach's alpha was 0.93.

Anxiety and depression symptoms. The Spanish version of the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale was used (HAD; Terol et al., 2007; Zigmond & Snaith, 1983). This scale comprises

14 items intended as a screening instrument to detect possible anxiety (7 items) and depression (7 items). Example items are: 'Worrying thoughts go through my mind' (anxiety) and 'I feel as if I am slowed down' (depression). Participants respond by selecting one of four alternatives that are scored from 0 to 3. Scores for anxiety and depression are calculated by adding the individual's responses to the items in each subscale, with higher scores indicating higher levels of anxiety and depression. The internal consistency values were $\alpha = .87$ (anxiety subscale) and $\alpha = .81$ (depression subscale).

Data Analyses

Independent samples *t*-tests were used to analyze possible gender differences concerning the use of eudaimonic and uncertainty metaphors. The relationships between the types of metaphors identified - eudaimonic metaphors and metaphors of uncertainty - and the participants' age, feelings of meaning in life, experiential avoidance, happiness and mental health were analyzed using Pearson's *r* correlation. In addition, the associations among meaningfulness, experiential avoidance, happiness and mental health-related variables were explored using Pearson's *r* correlation. All analyses were carried out using the statistical package IBM SPSS 19 and AMOS 16 (IBM, Armonk, NY, USA).

Results

No gender differences were found concerning the use of either eudaimonic ($t_{1534} = -0.47, p = .637$) or uncertainty ($t_{1534} = -1.34, p = .179$) metaphors (Table 1). The participants' age was positively associated with use of eudaimonic metaphors ($r = .29, p = .000$), and negatively related to uncertainty metaphors ($r = -.30, p = .000$).

Pearson's *r* correlations revealed that, as expected in H1, the greater endorsement of eudaimonic metaphors is connected with higher feelings of meaning in life, lower experiential avoidance, greater happiness, and better mental health (Table 3). Inversely and consistent with H2, uncertainty metaphors were negatively associated with feeling meaning in life and happiness, and

higher endorsement of this type of metaphors was linked to higher experiential avoidance and poorer mental health (Table 3).

Meaningfulness was negatively associated with experiential avoidance ($r = -.60, p = .000$), anxiety ($r = -.49, p = .000$), depression ($r = -.59, p = .000$) and general symptoms of mental health problems ($r = -.62, p = .000$), and positively related to happiness ($r = .69, p = .000$). Higher levels of experiential avoidance were connected with higher levels of anxiety ($r = .73, p = .000$), depression ($r = .72, p = .000$) and mental illness symptoms ($r = .78, p = .000$), and lower levels of happiness ($r = -.72, p = .000$).

Discussion Part 2

The results have confirmed that using one or another type of metaphor is connected with variables related to subjective well-being and mental health. In addition, the results revealed strong associations among meaningfulness, experiential avoidance, mental health and happiness.

Eudaimonic metaphors are associated with higher levels of presence of meaning, greater psychological flexibility, higher levels of happiness and lower levels of mental health problems. Endorsing uncertainty metaphors, conversely, is related to lower levels of meaning, greater experiential avoidance, and lower levels of happiness and mental health.

Understanding life as a journey, a gift, an adventure, etc. can make it easier for the individual to be aware of and identify valuable life goals and worthwhile experiences while fostering a sense of purpose. Eudaimonic metaphors, presumably, would also make it possible to integrate diverse life experiences into a comprehensible framework. In this regard, eudaimonic metaphors may offer a view of life that emphasizes the three components of meaning: comprehension, purpose, and mattering (George & Park, 2016; Martela & Steger, 2016). However, metaphors do not always provide a greater experience of meaning, as in the case of uncertainty metaphors. Using metaphors such as life is an enigma, a maze, a roller coaster, etc. would rather be communicating the experience of meaninglessness of the individuals who endorse them.

As presented, using one or another type of metaphor is not neutral but is associated differently with psychological variables such as meaningfulness, experiential avoidance, happiness and mental health. Although using metaphors is a common technique in clinical work and their potential association with desired therapeutic outcomes is frequently assumed, our study has empirically assessed such connections. In this regard, these results can be coherently integrated with proposals on the use of metaphors in ACT-based interventions (Stoddart & Afari, 2014; Törneke, 2017; Törneke, 2020).

General Discussion

Our study makes two main contributions. First, we identified two types of life metaphors, i.e. eudaimonic (e.g. life is a treasure, a journey) and uncertainty metaphors (e.g. life is a maze, a lottery). In addition, the dimensions of eudaimonia and uncertainty can be used to characterize, to some extent, other life metaphors such as fiction metaphors (e.g. life is a stage play, a dream) and confinement metaphors (e.g. life is a prison). Secondly, we found that the use of one or the other type of metaphor is not neutral, but is associated with different levels of psychological symptoms, anxiety, depression, and happiness. Furthermore, eudaimonic and uncertainty metaphors are differently connected with the presence of meaning in life and experiential avoidance.

In this research we aimed to integrate contributions from cognitive psycholinguistics, research on meaning in life, and from Relational Frame Theory (RFT) and its most notable application, Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT). In the latter, a central role is attributed to experiential avoidance as a psychological process involved in mental health problems. Interestingly, a bridge between RFT-ACT and cognitive psycholinguistics may be built. Cognitive psycholinguists have proposed that some kind of simulation processes are entailed in metaphors. For instance, Gibbs (2006) and Gibbs and Matlock (2008) suggested that the understanding of metaphors is rooted in body actions and sensations triggered by the source domain of a particular metaphor. Oatley (1999, 2001, 2011) considers metaphors as simulations that we run in our minds, similar to a computer

running a software simulation, with cognitive and emotional effects. This account of metaphors as embodied simulations could be pointing to an interesting hypothesis: to some extent, using a metaphor entails being exposed to bodily sensations, emotions, and mental representations, which may explain the connections between metaphors and levels of experiential avoidance. For example, understanding life as a treasure or a gift may be associated with the mobilization of sensations, emotions, mental images, etc. invested with positive value which may be linked to an attitude of approaching life. Conversely, understanding life as a prison could be related to experiencing aversive bodily sensations, emotions, thoughts, etc., which could be associated with flight or avoidance responses.

Previous studies within cognitive psycholinguistics have also allowed us to elaborate a list of metaphors about life that has been widely supported by the participants (Benczes & Ságvári, 2018a, 2018b; Hoffman et al., 2015, 2021; Hoffman & Acosta-Orozco, 2015; Köves, 2002; Kövecses, 2005, 2010; Kuczok, 2016). Our list of 19 metaphors included some items that, in Lakoff and Johnson's terms, can be called ontological metaphors (i.e. the concept of life is considered as a concrete object, entity or substance), and other metaphors that can be labeled as structural metaphors (i.e. the concept of life is structured or organized in terms of another semantic domain) (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980). For example, metaphors such as life is a gift or a treasure would be ontological ones, whereas metaphors, in which various facets or elements of the concept of life can be integrated and organized in terms of a journey, an adventure, a game of chance, or a war, would be structural ones. Cognitive linguistics research on conceptual metaphors has mainly focused on the analysis of how metaphors are constructed, their elements and the relationship that exists between the source domain and the target domain, thus adopting a metaphor-centered perspective. Our study's first part has tried to complement this approach by focusing on the metaphors' user, in which the focus is on the degree of endorsement that various metaphorical constructions receive. From this perspective, eudaimonic metaphors and uncertainty metaphors can include both ontological and structural metaphors. For

example, life is a gift is an ontological and eudaimonic metaphor, life is a journey is a structural and eudaimonic metaphor. Similarly, metaphors of uncertainty can be structural (e.g., life is a war, a game of chance), or ontological (e.g., life is a puzzle). The psychological effects of the interactions between types of metaphors, as a function of their construction (structural vs. ontological metaphors) and as a function of their use (eudaimonic vs. uncertainty metaphors), would be an interesting and original line of future research.

Previous literature on the concept of meaning in life offers interesting insights into how we construct metaphors about life. As discussed, the experience of meaning in life includes three components, i.e. purpose, coherence and mattering (George & Park, 2016; Martela & Steger, 2016). Metaphors about life include one or more of these components in one way or another. For example, life is a journey alludes to the idea of a journey towards a destination, goal, or objective, thus impinging on the propositional component. Understanding life as a school or teacher refers to the cognitive component, pointing to the learning and experiences that allow for a greater understanding of aspects of life (i.e. the coherence component of meaningfulness). Finally, understanding life as a gift or treasure would reflect the evaluative component, the consideration of life as something that matters and is valuable. Alternatively, believing that life is a maze, a game of chance, or an enigma would denote feelings of uncertainty or lack of a clear identification of purpose. Again, the way in which these metaphors about life are constructed can illuminate certain aspects. In numerous metaphors, for example, the idea of purpose has been articulated through the concept of "movement" or "displacement" from one point to another, i.e., employing a spatial structure. Here, eudaimonic metaphors, such as life is a journey or the course of a river, clearly imply this component of movement towards a destination. The spatial structure is also present in metaphors of uncertainty, although in this case, the movement is not linear from one point to another, but rather an erratic movement (life is a maze), or where, after more or less violent ups and downs, one returns to the same starting point (life is a roller coaster).

The results obtained have confirmed that both types of metaphors –eudaimonic and uncertainty– are significantly associated with the levels of presence of meaning in life. This finding is important for at least two reasons. First, it is an empirical confirmation of the hypothesis that we use metaphors primarily to make sense of and organize experiences in the manner of mental maps that allow us to navigate complex and abstract areas. In the case of eudaimonic metaphors, life is structured in terms of domains of origin that imply purpose, coherence and meaning while in metaphors of uncertainty the map makes visible characteristics of life such as its randomness or the uncertainty of its paths. Second, previous literature has consistently linked feelings of meaning in life to better mental health and subjective well-being, and conversely, has found that meaninglessness and uncertainty are associated with experiential avoidance and problems such as anxiety (Crego et al., 2020; Czekierda et al., 2017; Li et al., 2021; Glaw et al., 2017; Scannell et al., 2002; Schnell, 2009; Steger, 2017; Steger, 2018; Yela et al., 2020). Consistent with these findings, our results also yielded significant associations between eudaimonic and uncertainty metaphors and experiential avoidance, mental health and happiness.

Limitations and future research

The contributions of our studies must be weighed in the light of their limitations. A first limitation comes from the metaphors included in the research questionnaire. Although we have selected those metaphors that previous literature has identified as the most common when referring to life, we believe that the set of items used does not exhaust all possible metaphors. Thus, it is advisable to complement the approach followed in our studies with qualitative research. This would perhaps allow the identification of new types of metaphors about life as well as clarifying the role played by other complex metaphors (e.g. life is a dream, life is a theater, etc.).

Another limitation is the sample used where female participants and the relatively well-educated are predominant and therefore it is not statistically representative. Taking into account that social factors may be influential in the use of life metaphors (Benczes & Ságvári, 2018a, 2018b), this

could represent a potential source of bias. For instance, the fact that participants found metaphors appealing and meaningful could partly derive from the fact that a large proportion of the sample could be familiar with metaphors use and their cognitive/emotional correlates.

Our research used a questionnaire that included many different instruments which entails a risk of respondents experiencing fatigue or lack of focus in completing the scales. Prior to performing the analyses, we used the IBM SPSS Anomaly Detection software to identify unusual cases in the dataset but anomalies were not detected. However, a potential source of bias may lie in the possibility that those who completed the questionnaire were the most motivated subjects and those who experienced response fatigue could have abandoned the questionnaire before completing and submitting it.

Our research is cross-sectional and correlational, which is another limitation concerning the interpretation of results. Here, our study's second part only allows speaking of associations between the use of metaphors and psychological variables but not of cause-effect relationships. It would be interesting, therefore, to complement our correlational approach with experimental studies in order to analyze how the use of different metaphors can induce a variety of psychological effects. In this line, the contributions of Landau (2018) and Landau et al. (2014) are a reference.

The use of longitudinal and experimental designs would allow testing complex mediational models. In this regard, some hypotheses could be explored. For instance, the relationships between the use of life metaphors and well-being and mental health could be mediated by the levels of meaningfulness and experiential avoidance connected with the use of each type (eudaimonic/uncertainty) of metaphor. This mediational hypothesis could be based on previous research that has proposed meaningfulness and experiential avoidance as explanatory variables concerning well-being and mental health outcomes (Compton, 2000; Machell et al., 2015; Yela et al., 2020). Alternative hypotheses could also be plausible. For instance, a happy or healthy mindset may be what determines an individual's preference for the use of a particular type of metaphors. Even, circular logic could be

operating with particular metaphors (e.g. life is a treasure, gift) selectively orienting particular views of life (e.g. through increased focusing on positive/joyful aspects of life and neglecting of painful aspects) which could generate mindsets and subjective states (e.g. happiness) that in turn would reinforce the use of such kind of metaphors. These hypotheses on the mechanisms connecting the use of life metaphors with well-being and mental health deserve further exploration and, therefore, further research using appropriate designs for establishing causality is encouraged.

As above mentioned, the use of metaphors, analogies, narratives, etc. is frequently suggested as a therapeutic or intervention technique in order to promote a wide variety of cognitive and behavioral changes (Stoddard & Afari, 2014; Törneke, 2017). However, more research is needed to empirically analyze the effectiveness of these techniques and of intervention programs based on them. This would require the use of designs with pre- and post-intervention measures and, where possible, RCTs.

Our research leaves several more questions open to further research. It may be interesting to explore the role of mixed metaphors which combine aspects of both the degree of eudaimonia experienced and the degree of uncertainty. For example, the metaphor "life is a prison or jail" seems to indicate both meaninglessness and a high degree of uncertainty. It is also a metaphor strongly associated with high levels of experiential avoidance, low happiness, and high levels of anxiety- and depression-related symptoms. The identification of such a metaphor in a person's discourse could be very revealing from a clinical point of view.

In addition, it would be also compelling to further explore some aspects of how we construct metaphors of life, using the cognitive linguistics' insights from conceptual metaphor theory. Our studies have mainly focused on structural and ontological metaphors about life yet analyzing the role of life metaphors of an orientational type would be also worth researching. For instance, those metaphors in which "life is above" and its opposites or obstacles (death, illness, etc.) are "below". It would even be interesting to analyze the presence of these orientational elements in some metaphors

used in our study, such as "life is a building" or "life is a roller coaster", which imply an up-directionality in the case of the building, or up and down in the case of the roller coaster.

An interesting line of future research is the replication of the present research in different speech communities. As Kövecses (2005, 2015, 2017) and Kuczok (2016) have pointed out, metaphors in general, and those referred to the concept of "life" in particular, are markedly influenced by the culture milieu and context in which they emerge. Therefore, there remain open questions, i.e., whether life metaphors can be also grouped into eudaimonic and uncertainty metaphors in other languages, and whether similar metaphors are included in each category for the Spanish-speaking and other speech communities.

Eudaimonic metaphors and uncertainty metaphors were revealed to be independent, i.e., a person can endorse both types of metaphors to different degrees. This point opens up another interesting line of research. In particular, analyzing the possible interaction effects between eudaimonic and uncertainty metaphors deserves future research. In this regard, we could find out how different psychological variables are associated with four possible profiles: a) individuals who endorse eudaimonic metaphors but not uncertainty metaphors (i.e., high eudaimonia, low uncertainty), b) individuals who endorse uncertainty metaphors but not eudaimonic metaphors (i.e., low eudaimonia, high uncertainty), c) individuals who endorse both types of metaphors (i.e., high eudaimonia, high uncertainty), and d) those who endorse neither type of metaphor (i.e., low eudaimonia, low uncertainty).

Conclusions

Despite the possible limitations, our research has identified two types of metaphors (eudaimonic and uncertainty metaphors) and has empirically analyzed how the use of both types of metaphors is associated with different psychological variables, such as happiness, anxiety and depression symptoms and general mental health. Moreover, in line with the postulates of the cognitive approach to metaphors, we have identified that metaphors are indeed associated with the

presence of meaning, either by offering a map for understanding life (eudaimonic metaphors) or by revealing the difficulties that individuals encounter in their search for meaning in life (uncertainty metaphors). Complementing these findings, as current contextual models of psychotherapy have suggested, psychological flexibility (as opposed to experiential avoidance) is also connected with the use of life metaphors.

These findings are particularly relevant for applied areas of psychology, especially in clinical and health psychology, where metaphors may reveal how a person understands his or her life and may be a clue for possible psychological correlates concerning well-being and mental health. At the same time, metaphors can be a powerful tool for intervention. Metaphorically speaking, the psychotherapeutic process could be conceptualized as a journey from a starting point, i.e., the initial situation in which the patient uses a metaphor of uncertainty, to a final destination, i.e., arriving at a situation in which the use of eudaimonic metaphors is predominant.

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Figure captions

Figure 1.

Positioning metaphors in a two-dimensional orthogonal space generated by factor analysis.

Note: The numbers on the horizontal and vertical axes represent the factor loadings of the items (metaphors) on Factor 1 (eudaimonia) and Factor 2 (uncertainty), respectively.

Table 1.*Endorsement of Metaphors. Mean and Standard Deviation, by Gender, and Skewness*

	Total sample (N = 1536)			Female (n = 1276)		Male (n = 260)	
	Mean	SD	Skewness	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
<i>Life is a/ an...</i>							
box full of experiences	6.09	1.43	-1.80	6.10	1.41	6.03	1.53
journey	5.87	1.60	-1.53	5.88	1.60	5.87	1.61
school or teacher	5.68	1.70	-1.25	5.71	1.67	5.53	1.84
house or building	5.45	1.77	-1.02	5.44	1.77	5.50	1.74
treasure	5.43	1.98	-0.99	5.41	1.99	5.50	1.96
course of a river	5.37	1.78	-0.93	5.38	1.75	5.28	1.89
gift	5.35	2.09	-0.96	5.36	2.08	5.26	2.13
adventure	5.25	1.89	-0.90	5.25	1.88	5.25	1.95
roller coaster	5.23	1.96	-0.86	5.28	1.95	4.99	2.01
book or movie	5.13	1.95	-0.76	5.16	1.94	4.95	1.99
riddle or puzzle	4.79	1.97	-0.49	4.81	1.96	4.71	2.01
lottery or game of chance	4.66	2.11	-0.42	4.71	2.07	4.41	2.25
maze	4.62	2.13	-0.39	4.67	2.13	4.38	2.12
dream	4.36	2.14	-0.19	4.36	2.14	4.31	2.15
war or battle	4.29	2.18	-0.18	4.25	2.19	4.50	2.16
stage play	4.15	2.13	-0.08	4.13	2.13	4.26	2.11
carnival	3.66	2.13	0.24	3.68	2.14	3.58	2.10
sports competition	3.09	2.02	0.61	3.04	2.00	3.34	2.06
jail or prison	2.71	2.08	0.97	2.67	2.06	2.86	2.17
Eudaimonic metaphors	5.56	1.28	-0.98	5.57	1.27	5.53	1.34
Uncertainty metaphors	4.72	1.56	-0.39	4.74	1.55	4.60	1.61

Notes: For all variables, minimum score = 1, maximum score = 7; Standard Error for Skewness = 0.06

Table 2.*Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) Structure Matrix for Life Metaphors Items.*

	Three-factor solution			Two-factor solution	
	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 1	Factor 2
Explained Variance (%)	27.42	20.47	5.37	30.50	22.77
<i>Life is a/ an...</i>					
treasure	0.82	-	-	0.81	-
gift	0.82	-	-0.30	0.81	-
box full of experiences	0.79	-	-	0.75	-
school or teacher	0.67	-	-0.34	0.69	-
journey	0.61	-	-0.31	0.61	-
adventure	0.60	-	-0.59	0.67	-
house or building	0.57	-	-0.38	0.62	-
course of a river	0.54	-	-0.40	0.58	-
maze	-	0.85	-	-	0.85
riddle or puzzle	-	0.79	-0.30	-	0.81
war or battle	-	0.78	-	-	0.75
lottery or game of chance	-	0.64	-	-	0.66
roller coaster	-	0.61	-	-	0.65
jail or prison	-0.49	0.60	-	-	-
carnival	0.44	-	-0.77	-	-
stage play	-	0.36	-0.75	-	-
dream	0.47	-	-0.68	-	-
sports competition	-	0.49	-0.62	-	-
book or movie	0.50	-	-0.52	-	-

Notes. Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Oblimin with Kaiser Normalization. Items' loads below .30 are not displayed for clarity purposes. Items' stronger factor loading are bold typed.

Table 3.***Bivariate Correlations (Pearson's r) between Metaphors and Psychological Variables.***

	Meaning in life	Experiential avoidance	Happiness	Mental health issues	Anxiety	Depression
<i>Life is a/an...</i>						
box full of experiences	0.39***	-0.27***	0.37***	-0.31***	-0.23***	-0.34***
journey	0.34***	-0.29***	0.34***	-0.33***	-0.28***	-0.32***
school or teacher	0.37***	-0.26***	0.34***	-0.28***	-0.24***	-0.28***
house or building	0.35***	-0.25***	0.33***	-0.27***	-0.22***	-0.29***
treasure	0.57***	-0.45***	0.56***	-0.48***	-0.38***	-0.48***
course of a river	0.23***	-0.17***	0.23***	-0.19***	-0.16***	-0.20***
gift	0.53***	-0.40***	0.51***	-0.42***	-0.35***	-0.45***
adventure	0.34***	-0.32***	0.41***	-0.35***	-0.25***	-0.36***
roller coaster	-0.18***	0.22***	-0.18***	0.20***	0.23***	0.17***
book or movie	0.27***	-0.18***	0.27***	-0.24***	-0.20***	-0.25***
riddle or puzzle	-0.24***	0.29***	-0.26***	0.22***	0.25***	0.20***
lottery or game of chance	-0.16***	0.20***	-0.16***	0.15***	0.16***	0.11***
maze	-0.35***	0.43***	-0.38***	0.38***	0.39***	0.34***
dream	0.26***	-0.18***	0.25***	-0.22***	-0.18***	-0.24***
war or battle	-0.32***	0.43***	-0.40***	0.37***	0.36***	0.36***
stage play	0.04	0.01	0.05*	-0.04	-0.01	-0.04
carnival	0.24***	-0.22***	0.31***	-0.25***	-0.19***	-0.27***
sports competition	-0.05	0.15***	-0.08**	0.10***	0.10***	0.06*
jail or prison	-0.48***	0.55***	-0.54***	0.52***	0.46***	0.52***
Eudaimonic metaphors	0.55***	-0.43***	0.55***	-0.46***	-0.37***	-0.48***
Uncertainty metaphors	-0.33***	0.42***	-0.37***	0.36***	0.37***	0.32***

*** $p < .001$ (two-tailed); ** $p < .01$ (two-tailed); * $p < .05$ (two-tailed)